

PIANO PERFORMANCE AS A FACTOR ACTIVATING
YOUTH'S MUSICAL THINKING

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Abstract: This thesis talks about the acquisition of piano playing skills of future personnel studying in the field of education, problems in acquiring these skills and suggestions for their solutions.

Key words: general piano, skill, advanced pedagogue, reading from a sheet, accompaniment, ensemble performance, performance practice.

INTRODUCTION

The main task of the piano science taught in the music departments of higher education is to form and develop students' skills in playing the piano, as well as to train musicians-pedagogues who are mature in all respects, have a broad worldview, are highly cultured, have a deep aesthetic taste, and competence.

The piano is an instrument with a wide range and powerful sound, and no other musical instrument has such bright possibilities. Other musical instruments are mainly played with piano accompaniment. One of the great qualities of the piano is that you can play any kind of music on it. No matter what genre of music is written, there is sure to be an adapted version for the piano. The piano literature is also very numerous and extensive. .

In the words of A. N. Serov¹, a great composer, music is "the direct language of the heart." It illuminates all the richness of the reality around us. Sometimes it fills the heart of a person with a feeling of sadness and anxiety, sometimes with a feeling of joy and happiness." Piano compositions can show the same feelings. Especially, multi-voiced textures of piano compositions help the performer to develop harmonic and polyphonic hearing. Composer N.A. Rimsky-Korsakov² also put forward this idea in his article about the role of piano learning in the development of harmonic hearing skills.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

We mentioned above the relevance of learning to play the piano. But despite this, the current problem is that students of the music department pay

¹ Серов А.Н. Избранные статьи. Т. III. Музгиз, 1957,с. 121

² Римский-Корсаков, Н. Статьи (1869-1907).-СПб.,1911.-С.73.

more attention to their main specialty classes. However, in order to become a mature musician-pedagogue, in addition to specialized subjects, it is necessary to master the general piano subject as deeply as possible. It should be well understood that learning music and music literacy is a universal work, and the piano is the best, unparalleled tool for this. Learning music, like learning language, social science, mathematics, history, natural science, etc., should be mandatory for a cultured person.

N. G. Rubinstein said: "Each student can devote himself to mastering a certain musical instrument or subject, but he must study choral performance, piano skills, music history and aesthetics."

We think that the following factors can be a solution for students with different majors to acquire sufficient skills of playing the piano instrument:

1. Each student must have a piano lesson individually. The most important goal of individual education is to develop creativity.

"In order to learn to play musical instruments, it is necessary to have a certain set of musical abilities: to listen to music and be affected by it, to understand the main things in its content, to live with emotions expressed in music, to understand and understand the importance of means of expression in music.

But musical ability is not innate. It can be cultivated and improved by appropriate activities. "Playing a musical instrument is such an activity, in which the ability is not only manifested, but also formed and developed," said D. Rajabova.

It is necessary to try to help students studying in the music faculties of higher pedagogical education to develop their piano playing skills and achieve high levels in the process of performance. It is true that the requirements of the general piano course are much simpler than those of the special piano, but the works that are taken to tests, exams, and concerts are of a high level it should be processed: from the sound, technical, and artistic side. Students are graded based on the qualities listed above.

2. In order to achieve such results, it is necessary for the piano teacher to be very knowledgeable, skilled, creative, intellectually capable, and in tune with the times. For this, he needs to approach each student based on his psychology, abilities, and potential. A teacher should be such that students and parents respect him and be proud of him.

President Sh. Mirziyoyev also paid respect to the teachers and said³: "Dear teachers, passionate school principals, industry honorees, we consider you to be the support of the nation and we are always proud of you." Therefore, the teacher should always work on himself, teach using new pedagogical and innovative technologies.

If the solutions mentioned above are followed, or in other words, the suggestions, the student will start playing the piano skillfully. A student understands music deeply when he plays the piano himself. As B.V. Asaf'ev noted: "Practice is feeling from the inside and activates musical thinking." In this regard, G.G. Neuhaus left his opinion⁴. He stated:

"Emotional-imagery imaginations are awakened when a person performs by himself." We definitely agree with these thoughts. Because the student's impressions from his performance, his performance skills, practice, and movement develop his musical and artistic thinking.

CONCLUSION

Learning to play the piano is one of the important factors of musical education. This scientific article is devoted to the problem of learning to play the piano perfectly for students regardless of their major. Playing the piano activates young people's musical thinking. Learning to play the piano is especially useful for students in solfeggio, harmony, music analysis, piano and additional instruments (group), vocal and modern music, choir and choral studies, conducting. It will also greatly help them to work without difficulty in their future pedagogic work.

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⁴ Нейгауз Г.Об искусстве фортепианной игры.-М.;Музгиз,1961.-318 с.

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